

1 **Stereotyped compensatory feedback signaling is conducted by the MAP kinases MAP3K10-12.**

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7 We describe here stereotyped feedback signaling in response to genetic depletion of or pharmacologic
8 inhibition of target kinases in cancer cells. The cancer cells recall a developmental sequence during
9 compensatory signaling through *MAP3K10*, *MAP3K11*, and *MAP3K12*.

10 Citations

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